

THE ESA’s LUMIO MISSION: ILLUMINATING THE MOON’S DARK SIDE WITH IMPACT SCIENCE. E. Peña-Asensio¹, F. Ferrari¹, F. Topputo¹, S. Sughi¹, C. Giordano¹, P. Panicucci¹, G. Gomiero¹, A. Pizzetti¹, A. Martinelli¹, D. Koschny², E. Ammannito³, A. Zinzi³, R. Moissl⁴, R. Lasagni Manghi⁵. ¹Department of Aerospace Science and Technology, Politecnico di Milano, Italy (eloy.pena@polimi.it), ²Technical University of Munich, Germany, ³Agenzia Spaziale Italiana, ⁴European Space Agency. ⁵Università di Bologna, Italy.

Introduction: The Lunar Meteoroid Impact Observer (LUMIO) is a CubeSat mission designed to study meteoroid impacts on the Moon [1]. Developed under the European Space Agency’s General Support Technology Programme, LUMIO is a 12U CubeSat that will operate from a halo orbit around the Earth-Moon L2 point [2], providing continuous observations of the lunar farside. LUMIO is led by Politecnico di Milano and supported by the Italian Space Agency, the Norwegian Space Agency (NOSA), United Kingdom Space Agency, and Swedish National Space Agency. By detecting Lunar Impact Flashes (LIFs)—the brief bursts of light produced when meteoroids strike the Moon’s surface—LUMIO will extend the coverage of impact monitoring beyond Earth-based telescopes, which are limited to the nearside and affected by weather conditions [3]. See Fig. 1 for an overview of LUMIO.

The Moon, lacking an atmosphere, is constantly bombarded by meteoroids, ranging from millimeter-sized grains (hourly) to meter-scale objects (monthly). These impacts shape the lunar surface and pose a potential risk for future human and robotic exploration. Despite extensive ground-based monitoring, the impact flux on the Moon remains poorly constrained, particularly the latitudinal distribution and the millimeter to decimeter impactor size range [4]. LUMIO aims to address this gap by providing continuous, high-sensitivity observations, contributing to a more accurate characterization of the meteoroid population in cislunar space.

Instrument: The mission’s primary instrument, LUMIO-Cam, is an optical sensor capable of detecting meteoroid impact flashes in both the visible and near-infrared spectral range (450-950 nm). This will allow LUMIO to quantify the frequency, location, and energy of impact events, improving models of impactor flux [5]. Additionally, LUMIO will complement observations from NASA’s Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter [6], linking observed impact flashes with newly formed craters, and refining models of hypervelocity impact processes.

Experiments: In addition to its primary science mission, LUMIO will conduct two key technology demonstration experiments:

Autonomous optical navigation experiment. LUMIO will test an optical autonomous navigation system that uses vision-based techniques to determine its position relative to the Moon [7]. The system relies on a limb-based navigation algorithm, processing images of the Moon’s illuminated limb to

estimate the spacecraft’s location with sub-pixel accuracy. This experiment aims to reduce dependence on Earth-based tracking, demonstrating the feasibility of autonomous deep-space navigation for small satellites. The results will support future CubeSat missions requiring precise orbit determination without continuous ground station intervention.

Stellar occultation experiment. LUMIO will perform a stellar occultation experiment, using its optical system to observe stars as they are occulted by the Moon. The precise time of occultation measurements will be used to constrain the spacecraft position during science observations when the high solar phase angle reduces the accuracy of limb-based navigation techniques. Occultation measurements are expected to improve navigation accuracy, aiding in the absolute positioning of the LIFs and reducing the reliance on ground tracking [8].

Apophis flyby: LUMIO will be uniquely positioned to observe the asteroid Apophis during its near-Earth flyby in 2029. This event will present a rare opportunity to study the interaction of a potentially hazardous object with the Earth-Moon system. LUMIO’s instrument will be capable of observing Apophis for nearly one month before its close encounter and 2-3 days after it [9].

Science team: The Science Team consists of 62 members organized into six specialized working groups: (1) Meteoroid Characterization, (2) Surface Characterization, (3) Observation, (4) Impact Modelling, (5) Lunar Environment and Engineering, and (6) Citizen Science. Each group focuses on distinct research objectives aligned with the mission scientific goals.

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Figure 1. Overview of the LUMIO mission. Top left: Moon phases and main direction of incoming meteoroids in the Earth-Moon system. Center and top right: LUMIO mission phases. Bottom left: LUMIO quasi-halo orbit around Earth-Moon L2 (lateral view). Bottom right: expected apparent size of the Moon as seen from LUMIO.